

10.5281/zenodo.10639536

Vol. 07 Issue 01 Jan - 2024

Manuscript ID: #01213

FENG SHUI JEWELRY CONSUMPTION TRENDS OF GEN Z YOUNG PEOPLE IN HANOI CITY

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ABSTRACT

Feng shui jewelry is not only a fashion product, but also a part of lifestyle, bringing Gen Z youth in Hanoi cultural, spiritual values and profound meanings. In order to examine the feng shui jewelry consumption trends of young generation Z people in Hanoi city, the research team conducted this study. Through the results of the study, it can be seen that among those who know about feng shui jewelry, the number of people who have ever bought/used feng shui jewelry is only 46.8%. People who do not buy/use for documented reasons such as simply not liking to use it, feng shui jewelry needs to be preserved carefully and thoroughly, many people around have not used it, or using it requires sophistication, complexity... The number of people who have not yet used it and will buy and use it in the near future is still small. The frequency of using feng shui jewelry among young people is only at a normal level. Meanwhile, the favorite feng shui jewelry product is feng shui stone bracelets, followed by stone pendants. With the trend of simple, compact designs and reasonable prices being the top priorities when choosing products for young people. The main reason for young people to use feng shui jewelry is to attract fortune, luck, ward off bad luck, and be chosen as a gift. Many young people also agree that feng shui jewelry will bring fortune, luck and have a positive impact on health... so most of those who have bought/used it will intend to continue buying and using it.

KEYWORDS

Consumption trend, jewelry, feng shui, youth, generation Z, Hanoi city.

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1. Raising the issues

The feng shui jewelry market is of interest to young generation Z people, and the consumption of feng shui jewelry is gradually becoming a part of youth shopping culture. The products are not only beautiful but also considered a bridge between people and positive energy sources according to feng shui concepts, bringing many meanings to users such as: Shows aesthetics and class; Shows social status; Brings fortune and luck; Positive impact on health...

In this study, we will examine the feng shui jewelry consumption trends of generation Z young people in Hanoi city, young people of generation Z (born 1997 - 2012). Through the review process, the group captured the consumption trends that have been synthesized by previous studies, and conducted a survey in December 2023 to identify and evaluate those consumption trends through survey results. From there, the research team launched a number of discussions with feng shui jewelry traders to grasp the consumer trend towards spirituality and feng shui elements, bringing luck, fortune and health for consumers, especially young people of generation Z.

2. Feng shui jewelry and the meaning of feng shui jewelry

Feng shui jewelry

Feng shui jewelry is a combination of personal accessories with feng shui elements to bring fortune and good luck to their owners. Feng shui jewelry is designed in a diverse and rich way associated with accessories such as bracelets, earrings, rings, necklaces... with many designs and styles. (King Jades, 2021)

The feng shui jewelry set includes: ring, bracelet and necklace, a perfect combination that serves as a protective item to attract luck and advancement in business, career, and love. (Cafeland, 2022)

Feng shui jewelry is an accessory that not only shows the owner's style but also carries a spiritual element that helps the owner enjoy life, increase wealth, happiness and success. Currently on the market there are many types of feng shui jewelry with a variety of designs, colors and materials. Some popular designs include: Feng shui necklaces studded with quartz stones, pixiu bead necklaces... Bracelets, pendants, rings... studded with feng shui stones such as: Diamond, Swarovski, Topaz, Sapphire, Ruby, Emerald, Pearl... with a variety of colors for each destiny. (Ngoc Tham, 2021)

Meaning of feng shui jewelry

[According to Ngoc Tham \(2021\)](#), the benefits that feng shui jewelry brings to users are:

+ *Honoring aesthetic beauty and elegance*

The skillful combination of feng shui jewelry and fashionable outfits will certainly create a very prominent personal impression for the owner, contributing to expressing luxurious and noble beauty.

+ *Enhance status*

Feng shui jewelry is also a very important highlight to affirm one's position for the homeowner. Especially at parties and important events, wearing feng shui jewelry accessories will help the owner exude elegance and stand out from the crowd.

+ *"Lucky charm"*

They are considered "lucky charms" that dispel difficulties as well as attract good fortune. Therefore, owning these items with you will help the homeowner feel more secure, more peaceful, and achieve more fulfillment in life. Especially for business people and traders who are often interested in feng shui jewelry. They often buy jewelry with spiritual meaning, suitable for their destiny on the God of Wealth Day to help their business prosper and become more prosperous.

+ *Positive impact on health*

Feng shui jewelry is also a "precious medicine" that helps treat physical and mental diseases. In particular, feng shui gemstones also have a good effect in relieving stress so that the spirit is more relaxed and peaceful.

In addition, feng shui stones are feng shui jewelry used by many people. Feng shui stones help the spirit rise, create comfort, openness, and make the owner more sociable, so they can easily receive love from others. Because of this, feng shui stones can bring harmony and strength to emotional relationships between men and women, friends, relationships between colleagues, bosses and employees, family relationships (Ho Tien, 2021)

3. Research methodology

To examine "*Feng shui jewelry consumption trends of young generation Z people in Hanoi city*", the research team used two research methods including desk research (*review of documents published in the media*) and sociological investigation (*Collect answer sheets from young generation Z people born in 1997 - 2012 in Hanoi city, Vietnam*). The data will be synthesized and analyzed using Excel software.

Using the desk research method, the research team reviewed documents on feng shui jewelry consumption trends published in the media, domestic and foreign studies on the research topic. The research team developed a survey form to conduct a sociological investigation on feng shui jewelry consumption trends of young people of generation Z in Hanoi city, Vietnam.

The data collection method conducted by the research team is based on two methods: Convenience sampling method and "snowball" method - the method of finding the next subject based on suggestions or referrals of the object just surveyed. The survey was built on Google driver, and was conducted as a trial survey for 16 young people who regularly use feng shui jewelry to complete the survey and send the survey link.

(<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfH1pE1jiZaDxbPPv-O0uBwa8L1LcfFAOGEIn6HNwH6swky2A/viewform>) to Vietnamese young people of generation Z living in Hanoi city through social networks such as Facebook, Zalo, Email... The total number of survey questionnaires collected and analyzed was 277. Survey data were compiled and statistically compiled using Excel software, thereby analyzing and demonstrating the research problem. In addition, the research team conducted in-depth interviews with young people who are fashionistas and lovers of feng shui jewelry to supplement the basis for discussion.

4. Survey results of feng shui jewelry consumption trends of young generation Z people in Hanoi city

4.1. Description of survey participants

The subjects participating in the survey are young generation Z people in Hanoi city. The total number of votes collected was 277, of which 47 were male (17%), 223 were female (80.5%) and 7 did not want to specify (2.5%), which shows that the female gender has tend to pay more attention to feng shui jewelry.

Figure 1. Gender of survey participants

Source: The survey results

Regarding year of birth, the majority of survey participants were in the year of birth 2003-2007 with 228 survey participants (82.3%); 41 people were between birth years 1997-2002 (14.8%); 8 people were in the year of birth 2008-2012 (2.9%).

Figure 2. Age of survey participants

Source: The survey results

Regarding living area, 155 people live in the inner city area (56%) and 122 people live in the suburban area (44%).

Figure 3. Living area of survey participants

Source: The survey results

4.2. Trends in using feng shui jewelry

Regarding the trend of using feng shui jewelry, 235 people know about feng shui jewelry (84.8%) and 42 people do not know (15.2%).

Figure 4. Level of access to feng shui jewelry

Source: The survey results

The number of responses received was 235, of which 125 people had never bought feng shui jewelry (53.2 %) and 110 people had ever bought/used feng shui jewelry (46.8 %).

Figure 5. Level of purchasing/using feng shui jewelry

Source: The survey results

Regarding the reason for not using feng shui jewelry, 28 people realized that not many people around them use feng shui jewelry (22.4%); 27 people find that using feng shui jewelry requires sophistication and complexity; 39 people feel that feng shui jewelry needs to be preserved carefully and thoroughly (31.2%) and 65 people (52%) simply do not like using feng shui jewelry.

Figure 6. Reasons not to use feng shui jewelry

Source: The survey results

Regarding the choice of using gemstone jewelry in the future, of the 125 people who have never bought/used feng shui jewelry, there are 10 people who will buy and use it (8%); 54 people intend to buy and use (43.2%) and 61 people do not intend to buy and use (48.8%).

Figure 7. Rate of choosing to use feng shui jewelry

Source: The survey results

About the time to start using or buying feng shui jewelry with 110 people who have bought/used feng shui jewelry, 85 survey participants used it a long time ago (77.3%) and 25 people used it recently (22.7%).

Figure 8. Time to start buying/using feng shui jewelry

Source: The survey results

About the frequency of using feng shui jewelry by people around (friends/siblings), 8 people rarely use it (7.3%); 20 people rarely use it (18.2%), 69 people use it normally (62.7%); 8 people use it a lot (7.3%); and 5 people use it a lot (4.5%).

Table 1. Frequency of using feng shui jewelry

	1. Very little	2. Little	3. Normal	4. Many	5. So many	Average score	Frequency of using
Number of participants	8	20	69	8	5	2.83	Normal

Source: The survey results

Regarding the trend of using feng shui jewelry, 29 people choose feng shui stone rings (26.4%);79 surveyors chose feng shui stone bracelets (71.8%);33 people (30%) chose feng shui stone pendants, and 3 people chose other options such as stone statues (0.9%).

Figure 9. Type of feng shui jewelry that is loved/tends to be used

Source: The survey results

About the trend of using feng shui jewelry models, 81 responses showed that they are/like/tend to choose a simple, compact design (73.6%); 38 responses tend to choose diverse designs (34.5%);35 responses chose gemstone jewelry designed according to the buyer's request (31.8%); 53 high durability picks (48.2%); 55 responses show that feng shui jewelry has safe materials and has a clear origin; 34 respondents said they used it because of its sophisticated design (30.9%) and 62 respondents said it was reasonably priced (56.4%).

Figure10.Trend of using feng shui jewelry models

Source: The survey results

About the purpose of using feng shui jewelry, 91 answers used to attract wealth and luck (82.7%); 41 responses used it as a fashion accessory when going out or walking (37.3%); 48 responses were used as gifts for friends, relatives, and people around on special occasions (43.6%); 37 responses (33.6%) used for decoration (for products with beautiful, sophisticated designs...); 36 responses were used to improve health (32.7%) and 55 responses were used to ward off bad luck (50%).

Figure 11. Purpose of using feng shui jewelry

Source: The survey results

About the meaning of feng shui jewelry, 41 responses said that feng shui jewelry shows aesthetics and class (37.3%); 9 responses said that feng shui jewelry shows social status (8.2%); 93 responses said that using feng shui jewelry brings fortune and luck (84.5%); 56 respondents chose positive impact on health (50.9%); 1 answer said that feng shui jewelry brings aesthetics (0.9%) and 1 answer said that the meaning of feng shui jewelry is spiritual value (0.9%).

Figure 12. Perspectives on the meaning of feng shui jewelry

Source: The survey results

Box 1. Some impressions from those of you who have used feng shui jewelry

- BT1 ... Feng shui jewelry is very beautiful, diverse in color and has sophistication and solemnity ...
- BT2 ... Feng shui jewelry brings many feng shui and spiritual meanings, suitable for a person's destiny when worn, helping to attract fortune...
- BT3 ... Feel luckier and more secure when wearing feng shui jewelry ...
- BT4 ... Feng shui stones are very beautiful, the design is very elaborate and the meaning in each stone is very precious ...
- BT5 ... Feng shui jewelry is compact, easy to carry and highly aesthetic ...

Source: Survey results of research team

About the future trend of using feng shui jewelry of those who have bought/used, 100 people will continue to buy/use (90.9%) and 10 people have no intention of continuing to buy/use (9.1%).

Figure 13. Trends of surveyors in the coming time

Source: The survey results

Regarding the reason for not intending to continue buying/using feng shui jewelry, 4 people think that using feng shui jewelry needs to be sophisticated and complicated (40%), 3 people (30%) see that feng shui jewelry needs to be preserved carefully and thoroughly; 6 people simply no longer like to use feng shui jewelry and 1 does not have enough economic capacity (10%).

Figure 14. Reason for not intending to continue buying/using feng shui jewelry

Source: The survey results

5. Some exchanges and discussions

When conducting a survey, the number of women willing to participate in answering the survey was as high as 80.5%, showing that women are more interested in feng shui jewelry. The proportion of people who know about feng shui jewelry is 84.8%, however among people who know about feng shui jewelry, the number of people who have ever bought/used feng shui jewelry only accounts for 46.8% for the reasons noted as simply not liking to use, followed by feng shui jewelry that needs to be preserved carefully and thoroughly, many people around have not used it or the use needs to be sophisticated and complicated.

The number of people who have not yet used it and will buy and use it in the near future is still small. The frequency of using feng shui jewelry among young people is only at a normal

level. Meanwhile, the favorite feng shui jewelry product is feng shui stone bracelets, followed by stone pendants. With the trend of simple, compact designs and reasonable prices being the top priorities when choosing products for young people.

The main reason for young people to use feng shui jewelry is to attract fortune, luck, ward off bad luck, and be chosen as a gift. Many young people also agree that feng shui jewelry will bring fortune, luck and have a positive impact on health... so those who have bought/used it will intend to continue buying and using, a few do not intend to continue buying and using.

*From survey results on feng shui jewelry consumption trends of young generation Z people in Hanoi city, the research team came up with some **discuss with feng shui jewelry traders** to be able to grasp the consumer trend towards spirituality and feng shui elements, bringing luck, fortune, and health to consumers, especially young people of generation Z.*

- It is necessary to focus on researching the feng shui jewelry market to have a correct understanding and view of feng shui jewelry products. Help customers understand correctly about feng shui and feng shui jewelry. Feng shui is not superstition, feng shui needs to be understood as a Chinese science, dating back about 4000 years ago (Nguyen Kim Ngoc, 2024). Society is increasingly developing and people's lives are also improving. So feng shui is also known and learned by many people and is increasingly becoming a trend, and full of potential.

- Need to build **“Online Education Platform”** to provide extensive knowledge about spirituality and the meaning of feng shui jewelry. Young people in the digital age, access to modern technology is the optimal way to help young people learn about feng shui jewelry anytime, anywhere.

- The seller needs to do the work **“Spiritual Brand Building”**. Focus on business strategy with goals **“Strengthen trust”** to increase customer demand. Using media art to convey stories about the spirituality of feng shui jewelry, providing typical case studies and sharing positive experiences of customers who have used feng shui jewelry. Create trust and peace of mind for buyers when accessing the product.

- Build strategy **“Influencer”**. Carry out scientific education and spiritual consultation so that consumers properly understand the meaning and value of feng shui jewelry products. Cooperate with famous people who are successful and willing to share about the use of feng shui jewelry products. You can also invite other influencers such as feng shui masters or spiritual experts to share stories and personal experiences.

- Feng shui jewelry products will have a positive effect on each individual when the user must have the knowledge to choose the appropriate product, so **“Personal consultation”** plays an important role. Feng shui jewelry suppliers need to support customers in reading horoscopes, physiognomy, and feng shui to bring confidence and spiritual reinforcement to their products. Conducting personal consultation sessions to assist customers in choosing products that suit their individual needs is important.

Each feng shui jewelry product has different meanings, and is suitable for different audiences. Creating trust and personalization for each product will make it unique for each customer, is a direction that feng shui jewelry suppliers should take. Combining with communication, digital media, creating effects from influencers and spiritual partners will help feng shui jewelry businesses bring their products to more audiences, especially the youth.

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